

Who goes where? Researcher mobility by academic age, affiliation type and country

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Abstract

Analysing researchers' mobility is an important step toward understanding global research patterns and what drives researchers to move institutions, countries or leave academia. Here, an analysis of researchers' mobility during the years 2012 to 2021 was conducted through the lens of researchers' academic age. Data from three subject categories (finance, oceanography, and virology), where researchers are expected to publish under different affiliation types, were used. Changes in affiliation types (academic, corporate, government, etc.) throughout researchers' publishing careers were tracked. The results show that over 80% of authors did not change affiliation type over their career. However, of those authors that did exhibit changes, researchers were more likely to stop publishing completely with an affiliation type rather than adding a new type as their career progressed. At a country level, a comparison between authors initially affiliated with China and USA shows that, depending on the research field, authors initially affiliated with USA gradually stopped publishing under USA affiliations as their academic age increases. This effect was greater than that for initially Chinese affiliated authors in some subject fields.

Introduction

Mobile researchers contribute to the discovery process by sharing knowledge, expertise, and ideas with their fellow researchers at other institutions (Ferreira & Costas 2021). Researchers' mobility results in greater productivity and research impact (Alvarez, Rodriguez & Casado 2021; Halevi, Moed & Bar-Ilan 2015). However, researcher mobility leads to the migration of a highly-educated and skilled workforce to other institutions and countries (Khan 2021).

Researcher mobility can have many forms (Carrozza & Minucci 2014): research field, country, institution etc. Furthermore, there are different ways to be a mobile researcher (Carrozza & Minucci 2014). For example, Robinson-Garcia et al. (2019) distinguish between authors who leave their initial affiliations and those who gain additional affiliations while remaining affiliated with their initial ones. Institutional mobility tracks the movement of researchers between different institutions, but it could also reveal mobility between different institution (affiliation) types (academic, government, corporate, etc.).

There are various social, economic, and political reasons for one researcher to migrate to another country or institution (Siekierski, Lima & Borini 2018; Ioannidis 2004). Furthermore, there is a constant brain drain of academics – researchers are more likely to abandon academic institutions and continue their career in a corporate environment in the early stages of their publishing career (Boothby et al. 2021). This might be due to most early career scientists being recruited to fill short-term, rather than long-term, research roles (Boothby et al. 2021). There are also other factors that drive young researchers to abandon academia for other sectors (Chlosta et al. 2010). Many young researchers leave academia for better economic opportunities, uncertainty regarding long-term employment, stress etc. (Dorenkamp & Weiß 2017), which could be better in a corporate environment. Although an academic career is

considered attractive for young graduates, its appeal seems to decrease over the course of a PhD program (Sauermann & Roach 2012).

Regardless of the academic brain drain of researchers, there are numerous cases where academia-leaving researchers continue publishing work with non-academic institutions. An example being when a researcher begins publishing with a government or corporate institution after leaving an academic one. Consequently, a researcher might not be affiliated with an academic institution throughout their entire publishing career.

Here, the mobility patterns of researchers, in terms of the type of institutions they are affiliated with, are investigated within three different subject categories. Institutional, country-wise, and affiliation-type-wise mobility are considered with the aim of identifying field-specific and academic age-specific patterns in researchers' mobility.

Data & methods

For this analysis, data from Web of Science (WoS) were used. Articles for three contrasting WoS subject categories were selected: finance, oceanography, and virology, where researchers are likely to publish under different affiliation types. The analysis focused on articles published in the ten-year period between 2012 and 2021. WoS algorithmically generates unique author identifiers which makes author disambiguation efficient and easy to do. Authors who had published at least one article in the preceding three years (2009-2011) were removed so the dataset would better represent 'new' academic authors. Authors were given an academic age based on their publication record, where an age of one referred to the author's first year of publication. Subsequent calendar years would then age the researcher by one year (regardless of whether they published). Only authors with an academic age of five or more (i.e., one paper published at least in the fifth year after their first publication) were selected for the analysis. This filtration resulted in 35,597 authors for all three fields (7,900 in finance, 12,339 in oceanography, and 15,358 in virology).

Institutional affiliations for authors were taken from address data within WoS. These were then matched to one of six affiliation types (academic, corporate, government, health, research council, and partnership) using data from InCites Benchmarking and Analytics.

Data for all selected authors were aggregated according to academic age (i.e., aggregating authors at the same publishing stage in their career), allowing for a more nuanced understanding of mobility patterns.

Results

An example of one author's career is presented in Fig. 1. The author began publishing while at a health institution (2013) before switching to academic, corporate, and research council affiliations (2014). In 2015 the author switched to publishing under a government affiliation, then, in 2016, under academic, and in 2017 corporate and research council affiliations. Afterward, a two-year pause in publishing followed. In 2020 and 2021, the author published only under academic affiliations.

This author has three definitive career transitions in terms of affiliations – in 2014, when the author transitioned from a health affiliation to academic, corporate and research council ones, in 2015 when the author transitioned to a government affiliation, and in 2016 when the author transitioned from a government to an academic affiliation. There were other, though not definitive, transitions in 2017 (when the author added corporate and research council affiliations while continuing to publish under an academic affiliation) and in 2020 (when the author

dropped all affiliations except academic). After the first publishing year, the author added four new affiliation types (academic, corporate, research council, and government); however, all of these, bar academic, but including the original health affiliation, were also dropped by the final analysed year. It should be noted that transitions within an affiliation type (e.g., one university to another) were not considered.

Figure 1. An example of transitions in affiliation type during an academic career.

Considering the same author, another mobility perspective comes from the country level (Fig. 2). The author was initially affiliated with Australia (2013), then with China (2014), with the pattern repeated in the following two years. In 2017, the author remained affiliated with China but also added Belgium as an affiliated country. In 2020 and 2021 the author was only affiliated with China and USA, respectively.

Here, the author had four definitive career transitions in terms of affiliated countries – in 2014, 2015, and 2016 the author switched between China and Australia, and in 2021 the author switched to USA-affiliated institutions. Other, but not definitive, transitions happened in 2017, when the author added Belgium alongside China, and in 2020 when the Belgium affiliation ended. The author added three new affiliation countries after the first publishing year (China, Belgium, and USA). In the period analysed, Australia, Belgium, and China were eventually dropped as affiliations by 2021.

Figure 2. An example of transitions in affiliated countries during an academic career.

An analysis of affiliation patterns for the three WoS categories (finance, oceanography, and virology) is presented below. The general distribution of authors per affiliation types is shown

in Table 1. There is a lesser percentage of virology authors (79%) affiliated with academic institutions when compared with finance (85.8%) and oceanography (83.8%) authors. Another significant difference is in government affiliated authors: fewer authors in finance (6.8%) publish under a government institution than in oceanography (13.5%) and virology (10%). Less than 1% of authors published under a health institution in the fields of finance and oceanography, while almost 18% of virology authors were affiliated with a health institution. Only 1.25% of finance authors, and 5% of virology authors published with a research council, while this number goes over 10% for oceanography authors.

Table 1. Distribution of authors per affiliation types.

Affiliation type	Distribution of researchers (%)		
	Finance	Oceanography	Virology
Academic	85.81	83.86	79.02
Corporate	5.58	4.29	6.30
Government	6.84	13.51	10.02
Health	0.28	0.19	17.96
Partnership	0.04	0.20	0.28
Research Council	1.25	10.14	5.19

Most of the selected authors (92.7%) do not have a definitive career transition regarding affiliation type. Furthermore, most authors (82.5%) do not add or remove affiliation types during their careers. In finance, only 5.7% of authors have changes in affiliation types; in oceanography this number increases to 18.9%, and to 22.5% in virology.

When considering those authors that do have affiliation type changes, in finance, authors somewhere between the seventh and eighth academic year become more likely to completely remove an affiliation type rather than add new ones (Fig. 3, red lines). For oceanography (Fig. 3, blue lines), this breakpoint event happens after the fifth academic year; for virology, the sixth academic year is the breakpoint (Fig. 3, green lines). For finance, the proportion of authors that change, add, or remove affiliation types is around 10% for any given year of academic age, while for the other two categories, the proportion of authors slightly rises over time, and exceeds 13% in the tenth year of academic age.

Figure 3. Affiliation type changes against academic age. Dotted lines represent the removal of a given affiliation type; solid lines represent the addition of a given affiliation type.

Fig. 4 analyses mobility changes at the country level, by examining authors who are affiliated with either the USA or China when they first publish. In the case of finance, both China and USA have a decreasing trend of affiliated authors as academic age increases. Both countries have only a small proportion (less than 5%) of authors affiliated with other countries in their first academic year (i.e., authors affiliated to multiple countries via multiple institutions). When the academic age reaches the tenth year, only 80% of authors that began their finance publishing career in China remain affiliated with it. For those initially affiliated with the USA, about 90% remain affiliated in their tenth year of academic age.

In the case of oceanography, almost all authors initially affiliated with China remain affiliated with that country throughout the period. For authors initially affiliated with USA, the proportion that remain affiliated drops to 80% in the tenth year of academic age. For virology, authors initially affiliated with China tend to leave Chinese affiliations to a slight degree (dropping to 91.6% in the ninth year), but as their academic age approaches the tenth year, a greater percentage are affiliated with China (93.6%). For authors initially affiliated with USA the decreasing trend largely tracks that of China until an academic age of six, whereby USA affiliations continue to decrease with only 80% remaining affiliated by the tenth year of academic age.

Figure 4. Changes in affiliation, against years of academic age, for authors originally affiliated to either China or USA.

Discussion

Investigating researchers' mobility is important for understanding global patterns of science and innovation. The results presented here should be considered as an initial step towards better

understanding researcher mobility between different institution types and its correlation with academic age.

Two main conclusions can be drawn from the results. Among the authors that have affiliation changes during their publishing career, these changes are more likely to be the complete removal of an affiliation type as their career progresses. This is present for all three selected fields. The second conclusion is that mobility patterns can also vary between different countries. In the case of oceanography and virology, a greater proportion of authors initially affiliated with China remain affiliated with that country compared to their USA counterparts. USA is a global magnet for attracting foreign researchers (Huang et al. 2017), however researchers may return to their home countries in later career stages. China, on the other hand, applies policies focused on bringing back researchers (Chen & Li 2019). Depending on the field of expertise, some Chinese researchers are offered better opportunities in their homeland (Hao et al. 2017). In the case of finance, the situation is reversed – a slightly greater portion of researchers remain affiliated with USA as the academic age increases compared to their counterparts in China.

Further research is required to provide a more in-depth analysis of the correlation between the academic age of researchers and mobility patterns as well as the motives for publishing outside academia. The results obtained in this article do not necessarily have to apply for other disciplines, therefore investigating researchers' mobility in other fields is another direction of future research. Finally, additional analyses should be conducted to investigate the mobility between different affiliation types in the case of different countries and regions.

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